

LUDWIG-
MAXIMILIANS-
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MÜNCHEN

A FURTHER LOOK INTO QUENCHING: TEARING APART THE MAIN SEQUENCE INTO ITS BULGE, DISK AND GAS CONTENT

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and the CANDELS+GOODS+Herschel folks

THE MAIN SEQUENCE PROPAGANDA

(Schreiber, MP et al., 2015)

- Scatter is ~ 0.3 dex at all stellar masses and all redshifts up to $z \sim 4$
- Galaxies on the MS produce more than 70% of present day stars
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- Starbursts fraction is constant with z
- Account for $\sim 15\%$ of the CSFR

THE MAIN SEQUENCE BENDING

- A varying slope with redshift/mass

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(Whitaker et al., 2014 but see also Karim et al., 2011; Whitaker et al., 2012; Magnelli et al., 2014 and others ...)

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- Or a decreasing efficiency in converting gas to stars?

BULGES, DISKS AND GAS ON THE MAIN SEQUENCE

(Schreiber et al., 2016)

Sample:

CANDELS fields

$0.7 < z < 1.3$

$H < 22.5$ ($\text{Log } M_{\star} > 10.2$)

Spitzer/Herschel detections
($\text{SFR} = \text{SFR}_{\text{IR}} + \text{SFR}_{\text{UV}}$)

BULGES, DISKS AND GAS ON THE MAIN SEQUENCE

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- Corrected for \neq mass-to-light ratios of bulge and disk

$$B/T = (M_{\star} - M_{\text{disk}})/M_{\star}$$

B/T < 0.2 \leftrightarrow pure disk

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BULGES, DISKS AND GAS ON THE MAIN SEQUENCE

with bulges

BULGES, DISKS AND GAS ON THE MAIN SEQUENCE

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- “bending” still present with disks only
- bulges are not the answer

BULGES, DISKS AND GAS ON THE MAIN SEQUENCE

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Franco & Cox 86

Z: metallicity
FMR, Manucci+10

f: % of metals in dust
Leroy+08, Magdis+12

Assuming:

- single dust grain composition
- M^* - SFR - Z relation
- fixed value of f

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BULGES, DISKS AND GAS ON THE MAIN SEQUENCE

- Magdis+12 (z=2)
- ◇ this work (CANDELS z=1)
- this work (HRS z=0)
- Saintonge+11 (z=0)

slow downfall of SFE
in massive galaxies!

... TAKE ME HOME ...

- the Main Sequence has a varying slope
- flattens at high stellar mass and low redshift
- not linked to bulge growth or gas deficit
- due to a downfall of star formation efficiency